

EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION AS A PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTOR FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDEPENDENT THINKING OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. In this article, the fact that the role of theoretical thinking in the mental development of student-students is great. The fact that students learn to think, reflect and debate independently by reading and explaining literary works. It gradually talks about nature and society, about the formation of its own point of view, beliefs, views, critical thinking and its place in education and society.

Keywords: pedagogical cooperation, strategies of cooperation, teacher activity, design, pedagogical and psychological requirements, pedagogical skills, students.

Through the educational activities of students, a worldview, thinking are formed, a conscious attitude to the social system is formed. It is known that in the educational process, the activity of the student increases and his interest in educational subjects is formed. [1.50]

It is determined by achieving positive results in the educational process, first of all, giving scientific knowledge to the younger generation, carefully teaching their basics, creating a broad worldview and a scope of thought in them, and effectively organizing work on the formation of spiritual and moral qualities. In itself, this efficiency is inextricably linked with the organization, transfer, achievement of the process of teaching educational subjects in educational institutions. Also in the development of the competency of independent thinking of students of this process the seat is also distinctive. In particular, one of the main goals of the process of teaching socio-humanities is also to improve the quality of educational content on the basis of the development of independent thinking competence of students. [2.4]

The justification that their independent thinking plays a huge role in ensuring the mental and spiritual maturation of the younger generation has become an urgent scientific problem. In this sense, the psychologist scientists E.Goziev, V.Karimova, R.Sunnatova, Z.Nishanova, K.Kenjabaeva, pedagogues K.Husanboeva, N.Alavutdinova, M.Zainiddinova, Sh.Nurullaeva, M.Saidov, B.Noteworthy is the research work of scientists like Khodzhaev on the independence of reader thinking and its development. [3.35]

The concept of independent thinking, its role and role in the formation of personality, has been tried to reveal by the scientists named above. The issue has been commented on by psychologists, educators, at various levels and scales, based on their goals.

Each of the pedagogical scientists, who conducted research on the orientation of students to independent thinking, approached it in his own way, gave a definition. For Example, Z.In the opinion of nishanova: "Independent thinking as a personality trait is one of the important factors that ensure a high performance in achieving individual and collective achievements in any type of activity." [4.317]

And according to A. Erkayev views: "Independent thinking is the product and gift of the opportunities and freedoms that society creates for a person." Psychologist scientists V.Karimova and R.Circumcision has said of thought: "The feeling produced by the impact of events in the objective universe on the human mind is called "thought". On the basis of thought, the human eye will be able to see the mysterious aspects that are not directly progressing, that are not in sight of it, which, even in the event, are involved in the internal nature of that thing". [5.140]

Q.Husanboeva based on his own observations, defined independent thinking as: "Independent thinking is the mental activity of a person, relying on his knowledge and life experiences in accordance with clearly defined goals and objectives, aimed at solving the problem facing him independently, using various ways, methods, means, at the level of his intellectual capacity."

When we talk about the factors for the development of the competence of independent thinking of students, it is appropriate to think about their content, significance, giving result. So, in the development of the student's competence of independent thinking, attention should be paid to the following factors: [6.230]

First of all, it is necessary to organize lesson processes for students, which provide for the acquisition of the skills of independent thinking, Research, free expression of their own opinion, familiarization of peers with their own conclusions. It implies that educational technologies cover a certain area of pedagogical activity.

The sphere of activity, on the one hand, forms a system of rows that form its basis in accordance with the selected technology, on the other hand, emerges on the surface as a component of the activity. One of the main tasks of the new pedagogical technologies of today is the formation of the educational thinking activity of the student based on the content of modern education, that is, the provision of knowledge to students based on educational technology, guaranteeing the effectiveness of this process is one of the main issues. Such that that is, the organization of each course process carried out with separate preparation has a positive effect on the quality of education, this process serves to develop the student's competence of independent thinking. [7.41]

Secondly, it is necessary to make good, appropriate use of effective teaching tools in lesson processes. The essence of the pedagogical process is reflected in the content of the joint activities of the teacher and the student, in this process, the educator helps the student to overcome the difficulties that have arisen in such manifestations as publishing information, showing, reminding, giving insight or advice, directing, justifying, constituting, inspiring, expressing interest and respect, supporting exactingness. Each method selected for the course process affects the quality of Education. [8.16] When choosing a method, you should pay attention to:

- to the topic of the lesson (simple / complex);
- target to class;
- to lesson form;
- student population;
- student age;
- student experience;
- to resources;

- to the preparatory level of students;

The independence of thinking is inextricably linked with its productivity. If theoretical and practical tasks have been solved on advanced thoughts, ideas, recommendations related to a particular field, then such an idea is called productive. A reasonable assessment of the scale and quality of mental activity performed at intervals – serves as a criterion for measuring the productivity of reasoning. [9.145]

Even when a person thinks about ordinary things, their external signs are not limited to knowledge, and seeks to reveal the essence of events, he can also discover a common law from the reality of ordinary living. Obviously, the fact that independent thinking of a person has not yet been sought, that opportunities that are not fully exploited are discovered through human thought serve to accelerate the progress of Science and technology. [10.60]

Human maturation consists of the physical, moral and mental stages, and independent thinking is the last peak of the human maturation cocoon. At the present stage of mankind, mental maturation can occur in stages, gradually, at the expense of patterns of continuous activity, dedication of stable volitional behavior of the nervous system of tension, mental tension, emotional seriousness. [11.7610]

The development of the student's cognitive abilities is a priority in the process of teaching socio-humanitarian subjects, as in all educational subjects. [12.120]

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